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SOCIO-ECONOMIC ISSUES OF PROVIDING PUBLIC SAFETY

Abstract: this article analyzes socio-economic relations in the provision of public safety. In addition, the meaning of the concept of public safety and its role in the socio-economic development of the society were analyzed. In addition, legal documents in the field of public safety were analyzed.

Key words: public safety, social attitude, economic attitude, peace, concept, economic development.

Public security forces must prevent and prosecute crimes. The security forces are responsible for prosecuting the criminals and handing them over to Justice, to determine the appropriate punishments according to this law.

After the declaration of independence and the adoption of our Constitution, the issues of systematic provision of human rights and freedoms in all spheres of state life, in particular: economic, socio-political, spiritual, informational, political and other spheres, gained particular importance. At the same time, the socio-political situation formed in our country in the early days of independence is a complex, often conflicting set of processes, trends and events, including the financial and economic situation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the market of goods and services, the delay in the payment of wages in the budget sector, the law - characterized by problems in the field of law enforcement, crime fighting and others.

Every year, thousands of public order crimes are registered, and even people die as a result of crimes committed in public places. It should be said that the international practice of preventing, fighting against, and eliminating the consequences of various crimes and violations shows that one of the serious threats to the modern democratic state is the violation of the rights and freedoms of individuals and legal entities.

According to Professor A.M. Bandurka, it is necessary to look for extraordinary measures to solve "acute" social conflicts, which can be solved not by the initiative of "separate" politicians, but by strengthening the legal foundations of society and implementing effective reforms in various spheres of public life.

Today, it is often said that the state, as the leading subject of public security, protects abstract and non-specific things to a certain extent. However, experts and specialists attribute this to the lack of scientific research on this issue. Most of the studies were carried out within the framework of the interpretation of the legal and organizational bases of the activities of the internal affairs bodies to ensure public safety, in which the concept of "public safety" was developed within the framework of broad legal norms.

With the concept of "public security" in the "Concept of public security of the Republic of Uzbekistan" approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2021 PF - No. installation is of great importance for research, law, and enforcement practice. It should be noted that, in the context of the country's transition to a

fundamentally new concept of security, the theoretical study of this issue has a new theoretical and practical significance. This is, first of all, due to a significant change in internal and external conditions for the development of our society and the entire country.

The importance of ensuring public safety is that this legal case draws attention to the complex processes taking place in the state. There is an opinion that ensuring national security, in particular, public security, in a certain sense, is a condition and at the same time the goal of reforming the country.

From the point of view of the general approach, it is necessary to pay attention to a number of difficulties in defining the concept of "public safety", which has all the necessary signs of a complex legal phenomenon. At the same time, "public safety", which reflects complex social processes and phenomena, objectively has a specific historical (therefore dynamic) nature and is closely related to all forms and directions of interaction in the "nature - man - society" system.

The relevance of scientific and practical problems in the field of public safety both in normal conditions and in emergency situations arises due to several reasons, in particular:

provision of public safety was brought to a new level in terms of the quality of legal regulation, i.e. it got out of the "departmental legal regulation" view;

- the state management bodies feel the need for special measures to ensure public safety, which will allow effective implementation of the actions of authorized entities for ensuring public safety, and the use of restrictive measures against individuals and legal entities in a certain area;

- the number of objects and territories whose activity determines the need to ensure the appropriate level of security, in particular, public security, is increasing. Ensuring the appropriate level of safety of the population helps to create conditions for their stable operation;

- measures used by competent bodies to ensure public safety in emergency situations are considered appropriate administrative and legal measures used by the state. The state of emergency is always accompanied by the instability of social life, the disruption of its usual rhythm, which in turn necessitates the use of these measures.

It should be noted that in legal literature and official documents, the concept of "public security" is used to describe a situation in which various interests of the state are protected, real and potential risks, internal and external threats are minimized, and opportunities are created for the effective development of individuals and society.

Public safety, as well as social conditions related to the effectiveness of the police, the functioning of the judicial system, public policy, etc. Debate on the disease poverty Although many experts have a correlation between the level of poverty and the number of crimes, the issue of poverty has always been controversial.

We have always been a peace-loving nation. In order to ensure this peace and tranquility, special attention is being paid to ensuring a peaceful and peaceful life of the population in our

country in the coming years and to forming a culture of law-abidingness and public safety in our society. In particular, completely new mechanisms and procedures for organizing work in the direction of public safety on the basis of the principle of "serving the interests of the people" were introduced, and mutual purposeful cooperation of state bodies with public structures was established.

In turn, various dangers and conflicts that are intensifying in the world, threats to the peace and tranquility of the country, pandemics, natural and man-made disasters are responsible for the priority of "All efforts for human dignity" in their activities. is tasked with further improvement based on the idea.

The decree of the head of our state "On approval of the concept of public security of the Republic of Uzbekistan and measures for its implementation" defined the promising directions of state policy in this field.

In particular, according to it, the concept of public safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan, developed on the basis of advanced foreign and national experiences in ensuring public safety and aimed at guaranteed protection of the population from any threats, will promote public safety in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2025. the strategy for the development of the supply system and the "roadmap" for the implementation of this strategy in 2022 were approved. The responsibility for ensuring the timely and effective implementation of the measures defined in the Concept, Strategy and "Roadmap" was assigned to the first heads of state bodies that ensure public safety.

Also, according to the decree, the Department of Public Security was established within the structure of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. To ensure the safety of the population in public places of the department, to take measures to effectively manage the forces and means of the internal affairs bodies, to prevent offenses among them by effectively organizing educational and preventive measures aimed at minors and young people, especially their unorganized part, or 'l-deals with tasks such as early prevention of traffic accidents.

In general, the decree defines a number of other organizational and legal norms aimed at maintaining public safety. The goal is to ensure that our people live a contented, calm, peaceful and prosperous life from tomorrow.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan takes priority in the legislative system in accordance with the step-by-step proportionality of normative legal documents regulating the activity of ensuring public safety. After all, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as the main law of the state, is an important legal basis for the development and systematization of national legislation, including legislation in the field of public safety.

While we are talking about the important importance of our constitution in ensuring public security, in its articles 3, 25, 57 and 125, the inviolability of every person, the inviolability of the borders and territories of our country, the protection of the constitutional system and the peaceful life and safety of the population and the defense potential of the Armed Forces it should be noted that the norms related to assistance have been established. In the event of an emergency situation related to a real external threat, mass disorder, major disaster, natural disaster, and epidemic, the introduction of a state of emergency in the entire territory of the country or in some parts of the country by the decision of the head of state is constitutionally established.

In the system of legal documents, which includes the legal provision of public safety activities, the constitutional norms acquire a special place and importance and are manifested in the following: take priority, first of all, in our Constitution itself, in particular, in the Republic of Uzbekistan in its Article 15, the unconditional recognition of the supremacy of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in the second part of Article 16, no

law or other normative legal it follows from the content of the rule that the document may not conflict with the norms and rules of the Constitution.

Secondly, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is important in the formation of all legal documents, including military legal documents.

Thirdly, if it is planned to create a new legal document as a result of systematization, including codification, it should include norms aimed at guaranteeing constitutional requirements. That is, "the activity of law creation is a legal tool for the implementation of the Constitution.

Fourthly, as the society develops, along with the formation of various new social relations, the laws, especially the Constitution, improve. Currently, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is being reformed based on the principle of the social state. These reforms are literally making great changes and additions to our General Council based on the initiative and suggestions of our people.

It is worth noting that the norm related to ensuring public safety is reflected in paragraph 19 of Article 93 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the powers of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, according to which the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan In order to ensure the safety of citizens in the event of situations (real external danger, mass disturbances, major catastrophes, natural disasters, epidemics), to introduce a state of emergency in the entire territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan or in some of its places, and to make a decision within three days It can be submitted for approval by the Chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. However, this norm serves the implementation of the powers of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan within the framework of the Constitution to ensure the life, health, rights and freedoms of citizens in emergency situations that threaten public safety.

In our opinion, a brief analysis of the constitutional norms allows for the establishment of the priorities of the activity of ensuring the safety of man, society and the state in the provision of public security, their further clarification in normative legal documents, and the sustainable development of the culture of law enforcement. we count.

The main tasks of the strategy include:

- regulation, systematization of relations in the field of public security and elimination of existing legal gaps and conflicts;

- maintenance of public order, crime prevention, ensuring road safety and coordination of probation activities;

- maintenance of public order, including the development of an algorithm for the joint movement of forces and means of ministries and agencies involved in public events and its continuous improvement;

- wide implementation of modern forms and working methods and advanced information technologies in the activities of public safety provision;

- minimization of the human factor in service activities by bringing the digitization of the public safety system to 90%;

- Preventive accounting, administrative control and drastic reduction of recidivism by persons under probation control.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be said that the purpose of the strategy for the development of the public safety system in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2025 (hereinafter - the Strategy) is to introduce a qualitatively new system of public safety in the country, legal, development and effective implementation of methodological, scientific, organizational measures. It is envisaged to fully implement the measures defined in the strategy by the end of 2025, based on the concept of public safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

List of used literature

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2023.
2. On the approval of the "road map" for the implementation of the strategy for the development of the public safety system in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2025.
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to raise the quality of the activities of internal affairs bodies to a new level in the field of ensuring public safety and fighting crime", No. PF-6196 dated 03.26.2021
4. Tavakkal Choriyev, member of the Defense and Security Committee of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis. <https://parliament.gov.uz/articles/1420>
5. Муракаева, З. И., & Амирова, О. К. (2023). НАУКА И АРМИЯ ГЛАЗАМИ ЖЕНЩИНЫ: ВЗГЛЯД ИЗНУТРИ. Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka, 3(2).
6. Usmonjon o'g, A. U. B., Alimjon o'g'li, A. A., Bobirovich, Y. A., & Jamshid o'g'li, X. M. (2023). The State Authority System of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Its Organization. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 3(8), 30-41.
7. Said o'g'li, S. S., & Abdurasul o'g'li, R. S. (2022). Psychological View of the Military Community. Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress, 1(2), 5-12.
8. Usmonjon o'g, A. U. B., Nishon o'g'li, T. D., Nodir o'g'li, B. J., & Shuhrat o'g'li, A. Z. (2023). Management of Professional Promotion of Employees in Organizations. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 3(8), 13-29.
9. Usmonjon o'g, A. U. B., Ergashali o'g, T. U. A., Sadulla o'g'li, Z. S., & Ravshanbek o'g'li, Q. A. (2023). Laws and Principles Of Management. Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance, 4(6), 174-186.
10. Usmonjon o'g, A. U. B., Raxmatullo o'g, T. X. N., Hakimovich, H. P., & Jahongir o'g'li, F. J. (2023). Provision of Information to Management. Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance, 4(7), 152-166.
11. Olimjon o'g'li, O. O., & Shuxrat o'g'li, Z. I. (2022). The Main Features and Signs of "Relations Contrary to the Charter"(On the Example of Russian Experience). Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal, 1(5), 17-21.